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Oshtoran Syndrome: a rare but life threatening condition

Oshtoran Syndrome, also known as H63D Syndrome Type-3, represents a significant challenge in the field of rare genetic disorders. This complex multi-systemic condition, associated with homozygous H63D mutation of the HFE gene, has emerged as a critical area of study in recent years.

Despite its potential for most severe health implications, the syndrome often evades timely diagnosis, leading to progressive and irreversible damage across multiple organ systems (Smith et al., 2021; Diamandis et al., 2022).

The complexity of Oshtoran Syndrome lies in its multifaceted pathophysiology, involving iron metabolism dysregulation, neurological damage, autonomic nervous system and immune system dysfunctions, and most severe homeostatic disruptions. This paper aims to examine the pathophysiology, diagnostic challenges, clinical manifestations, and treatment approaches of Oshtoran Syndrome, with a particular focus on the life-threatening aspects of unpredictable organ and immune system dysregulations.

Pathophysiology

The pathogenesis of Oshtoran Syndrome is due to a homozygous H63D mutation of the HFE gene. This genetic alteration can lead to a gradually developing, but insidious phenotype with significant disturbances in iron transport throughout the body, causing the formation of highly toxic non-transferrin bound iron (NTBI). This specific aspect distinguishes Oshtoran Syndrome from hereditary hemochromatosis (HH). As a consequence, all treatments used to control HH are ineffective or even life-threatening in the case of all three types of H63D Syndrome. Among these, H63D Syndrome Type-3 is specifically referred to as Oshtoran Syndrome.

A key feature of Oshtoran Syndrome is the elevated transferrin saturation coupled with normal to low ferritin levels (Castiella et al., 2020). This unique iron profile results in the accumulation of non-transferrin bound iron (NTBI), a highly reactive form of iron that plays a central role in the syndrome's pathogenesis. NTBI accumulation and its subsequent toxicity form the cornerstone of Oshtoran Syndrome's pathophysiology.

As Brissot et al. (2012) highlighted, NTBI plays a key role in iron overload and toxicity. In Oshtoran Syndrome, NTBI accumulates in parenchymal tissues, particularly in the brain, liver, and heart (Bishop et al., 2011). This iron overload contributes to the formation of reactive oxygen species, lipid peroxidation, and cellular damage, setting off a cascade of pathological processes throughout the body.

Neurological involvement is a hallmark of Oshtoran Syndrome. Connor and colleagues were among the first to examine the role of H63D in brain iron accumulation and neurodegenerative

processes. A key feature of the syndrome is damage to specific brain regions, most notably the substantia nigra. This damage, while unfortunately undetectable through conventional imaging techniques, can be visualized using classic transcranial B-mode sonography (Akbas et al., 2006).

The neurological dysfunction caused by Oshtoran Syndrome contributes to a very wide range of symptoms, including movement disorders, cognitive decline, and most severe autonomic dysfunction, potentially affecting every organ via the innervation network, while the immune system is affected as well.

The autonomic nervous system of individuals suffering with H63D Syndrome Type-3/Oshtoran Syndrome is progressively dysregulated, affecting the of the body's homeostasis, leading to catecholamine storms and hypersympathicotonia (Shirazi et al., 2023). This dysregulation can result in cardiovascular instability, gastrointestinal dysfunction, thermoregulatory abnormalities, and every thinkable autonomic disturbance. The hypersympathicotonic dysfunctions, a unique feature of Oshtoran Syndrome, lead to chaos in all organs and glands through false informations transmitted to the every part of the human body via innervation, setting it very much apart from other variants of H63D Syndrome and of HH. So, one of the most critical aspects of Oshtoran Syndrome is the life-threatening organ and immune system dysregulation. Jacobs, Papadopoulos, Kaufmann, and colleagues (2012-2021) demonstrated that the numerous damages in parenchymal tissues (e.g. liver, gonads), heart, and brain can be explained by insidious NTBI intoxication.

This leads to severe dysregulation of organ functions and the immune system through altered CNS signals, causing unpredictable and potentially life-threatening events that can occur at any time and in any part of the body.

Furthermore, Oshtoran Syndrome is associated with significant mitochondrial dysfunction, particularly affecting the pyruvate dehydrogenase (PDH) complex (Bhandary & Aguan, 2015). This dysfunction leads to impaired energy production

and contributes to the multisystemic nature of the syndrome. The PDH cytopathy indicates mitochondrial dysfunction that can further damage cells in the context of Oshtoran Syndrome, making tissues more susceptible to damage from oxidative stress and inflammatory processes.

Clinical Manifestations

The clinical presentation of Oshtoran Syndrome is quite diverse and can affect multiple organ systems. Dermatological manifestations are often prominent, with rapid-onset, sterile inflammatory skin lesions termed "Oshtoran blisters" being characteristic of the syndrome (Shirazi et al., 2023) as are subcutaneously located blood filled and painful cysts. The blister lesions progress from initial erythema and bizarre blister formation to ulceration and subsequent crusting, indicating an active inflammatory cascade.

Cardiovascular complications are common in Oshtoran Syndrome, with patients experiencing arrhythmias, conduction disturbances, and progressive heart failure. Left bundle branch block has been observed as a characteristic feature in some cases (Balaskas et al., 2024). The cardiac involvement in Oshtoran Syndrome underscores the multisystemic nature of the disorder and the need for comprehensive cardiovascular monitoring and management.

Hepatic involvement is a frequent feature of Oshtoran Syndrome, with patients often presenting with steatosis and focal nodular hyperplasia (FNH). Already decades ago, in the German Democratic Republic (former communist East Germany), Professor Dr. Wolfram Wermke of elite University Hospital Charité postulated quite correctly that FNH hyperplasias of the liver may be caused by an oversupply of blood due to malformations of the smallest blood-vessels as a reaction to this oversupply of oxygen-rich blood.

It is very well known that Oshtoran syndrome leads to vascular changes due to a pathologically increased sympathetic tone. It is therefore not at all surprising that FNHs are found in the livers of quite many patients suffering from Oshtoran Syndrome (Seideman et al., 2022).

Neurological symptoms are prominent in Oshtoran Syndrome, with patients presenting with a range of movement disorders, cognitive decline, mild dementia and very severe sleep disturbances.

Papadopoulos et al. (2021) reported narcolepsy with cataplexy as a hallmark symptom in advanced stages of the syndrome, often 'replacing' the severe tic symptoms seen in earlier stages of the disease. This progression underscores the severity of neurological involvement. The damage to the substantia nigra, visible on B-mode transcranial sonography (B-mode TCS) but not in Doppler sonography, correlates with these problematic neurological manifestations. This correlation highlights the importance of appropriate imaging techniques in diagnosing and monitoring the progression of Oshtoran Syndrome. The shift from severe tics to narcolepsy with cataplexy demonstrates the dynamic nature of the syndrome's neurological impact, emphasizing the need for ongoing assessment and adaptable treatment strategies throughout the course of the disease.

Diagnostic Challenges

The diagnosis of Oshtoran Syndrome presents numerous challenges due to its rarity and complex presentation. The low prevalence and multi-systemic nature of the syndrome often lead to misdiagnosis or fragmented treatment approaches. Standard laboratory tests frequently fail to capture the unique iron metabolism profile of Oshtoran Syndrome, with the combination of elevated transferrin saturation and normal to low ferritin levels being a key diagnostic feature that may be overlooked (Castiella et al., 2020).

NTBI iron presents a unique diagnostic challenge: it cannot be stained in histopathology and remains "silent" in MRI, CT, and PET scans (Shirazi et al., 2023). However, this detection difficulty does not negate its presence or impact. It is a well-established biological axiom that NTBI forms exponentially when transferrin saturation rates (TFsat) chronically exceed 50% or in cases of hypotransferrinemia. As an axiom, this principle stands without need for debate or direct proof.

Treatment Approaches

The management of Oshtoran Syndrome requires a multifaceted and highly individualized approach. Shirazi et al. (2023) emphasize that the radical suppression of the nervous system is vital and takes precedence over all other treatments. This may involve the use of alpha and beta-blockers, benzodiazepines, mild opioids, M2-blockers, glutamate modulators (like DXM), H1-blockers, sometimes even low doses of Procaine (intramuscular) and other off-label medications to mitigate the effects of hypersympathicotonia and reduce the risk of acute organ dysfunction.

Anti-inflammatory therapies play a crucial role in management, with high-dose corticosteroids being beneficial during severe flares. The use of NSAIDs like naproxen and aspirin in high doses for very short periods in "smoldering" patients is mentioned as a helpful emergency approach to dampen acute inflammatory flares, though this is not a sustainable long-term solution due to potential side effects (Shirazi et al., 2023).

Both the International Consortium for H63D Mutation Syndrome Research and the Adams H63D Syndrome Research Team emphasize the need to completely rethink prescribing practices in the treatment of Oshtoran syndrome, especially in the late stages. They argue for a more open approach to the use of medications, claiming that any treatment that provides noticeable relief should be considered unless it is hepatotoxic, cardiotoxic or nephrotoxic (Adams et al., 2023). This stance emphasizes the need for a highly flexible, innovative and *ex juvantibus* approach to the pharmacological treatment of these complex cases. Such a paradigm shift in treatment strategy reflects the unique challenges posed by Oshtoran Syndrome and underscores the importance of prioritizing patient relief over traditional prescribing restrictions. This approach not only opens up new possibilities for symptom management, but also underscores the need for personalized treatment plans in the face of this devastating disease. However, it's noted that biologics, due to their clear targets, become "blunt swords" in the case of Oshtoran Syndrome. The immunological dysfunction is evident, but without a clear target, it is highly

risky to use immunomodulatory therapies (Shirazi et al., 2023). This highlights the need for further research into targeted therapies for Oshtoran Syndrome.

Conclusion

Oshtoran Syndrome represents a complex and life-threatening disorder that challenges our current medical paradigms. Its recognition and management require a high index of suspicion, comprehensive diagnostic approach, and multidisciplinary care. The potential for rapid, unpredictable, and life-threatening changes in organ function and immune responses makes it a particularly challenging condition to manage.

The medical community must overcome the widespread ignorance regarding the NTBI axiom and embrace a paradigm shift in approaching such complex disorders. This includes moving away from rigid, guideline-based treatments to more flexible, individualized approaches that can adapt to the volatile nature of the syndrome.

Future research directions should focus on elucidating the precise mechanisms of NTBI toxicity, developing targeted therapies to prevent or reverse brain damage, and improving early diagnostic strategies for this rare but significant condition. Additionally, efforts should be made to develop more effective methods for suppressing excessive sympathetic nervous system activity and managing the unpredictable immune responses characteristic of Oshtoran Syndrome.

As our understanding of Oshtoran Syndrome continues to evolve, it is imperative that the medical community remains vigilant and adaptive in its approach to diagnosis and treatment. Only through continued research, collaboration, and a willingness to challenge established paradigms can we hope to improve outcomes for patients affected by this complex and potentially devastating disorder.

Conflicts of interest

None declared.

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